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Implementation of Project Hatid Pangarap: An Assessment

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Abstract

This study, which aimed to evaluate the implementation Project HATID PANGARAP was conducted at Hulo Integrated National High School and Hulo Elementary School during the first quarter of School Year 2024-2025. The researcher used descriptive method of research with online survey questionnaire as the main instrument which was sent to the thirty (30) teachers who served as respondents and who evaluated the program with respect to its objectives, program process, community involvement, and monitoring and evaluation. The results showed that respondents' evaluation obtained a grand mean of 3.90 and verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree which indicate the all the evaluated aspects were contributing factors in the success of its implementation. Likewise, the findings infer that Project HATID PANGARAP has a clear vision, utilizes well-crafted process, involves the educational community, and uses mechanisms to assess its strengths and weaknesses. The respondents suggested for the school to conduct intensify more the dissemination of information to reach more stakeholders who can take part in the program and provide benefits to a larger number of learners.

Keywords: *evaluation, school program, community involvement*

Introduction

Absenteeism is a major and ongoing issue in the country's academic community. It has a major impact on the learning of the students because the higher the number of absences the students acquire, the less lessons the students will be able to participate in class. This would also imply that there would be fewer and more disconnected concepts of learning. Students who are regularly absent are more likely to drop out of school at a young age and will not continue their education, which may lead to unemployment, low average incomes, and poverty in the country.

In fact, in many parts of the Philippines, particularly in rural and remote areas, poverty is a significant driver of absenteeism. Families struggling with financial hardships may require children to miss school to work and contribute to the household income or care for younger siblings. The lack of basic necessities, such as food, clothing, and school supplies, further exacerbates the problem, making regular school attendance difficult for many students.

Relatively, geographical challenges also play a crucial role in student absenteeism. In rural areas, students often face long and difficult commutes to school, sometimes traveling by foot through mountainous terrain or crossing rivers. The physical distance and lack of reliable transportation can lead to irregular attendance, especially during adverse weather conditions.

The effects of student absenteeism in the Philippines are far-reaching. It not only hinders individual students' academic progress, but it also has an impact on the country's overall educational quality. High absenteeism rates are linked to lower academic achievement, higher dropout rates, and fewer future opportunities, perpetuating the cycle of poverty and inequality.

In this regard, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued polices and orders which aim to address this pressing problem in the educational system. It is clearly stated in DepEd Order No. 47, series of 2010 that schools are required to closely monitor student attendance and teachers must keep accurate records of attendance and identify students who are frequently absent. In addition, schools are encouraged to implement their own initiatives and programs to reduce absenteeism. These can include incentives for good attendance, remedial classes, and peer support groups.

In the case of Hulo Integrated National High School and Hulo Elementary School, learners experience limitation as regards their access to quality education because of some factors like financial constraint and proximity of the school to their houses leading to their constant absenteeism and to be identified as learners at risk of dropping out. As early as the first quarter of this school year, these problems are very evident resulting as well to poor academic performance of the learners.

The role of stakeholders in education sector is crucial in promoting basic quality education. The Department of Education believes that the support provided by our education partners is a big contribution to its internal and external operation to achieve its goal.

To provide the greatest education possible for all students, we should form partnerships. Partnerships are formed for a variety of reasons, including improving public relations, obtaining additional financing, and advancing a specific cause or concern. Some partnerships are formed through a formal structure, while others are formed through an unwritten agreement or handshaking. The mission statements or educational goals of the department incorporate collaborations with students' families and communities.

Hence, Project HATID PANGARAP (Promoting A Nurturing and Guiding Approach for a Responsive and Active Pilillanon) is initiated. This program basically aims to provide assistance through free transportation to less fortunate students promote inclusivity and equality within the education system.

The proponent of this initiative wished to determine the areas in which the program can still be improved and identify the valuable assessment of the teachers regarding its implementation during the first quarter. With these reasons, she opted to conduct this study with the goal of evaluating the program and gather vital recommendations to increase the efficiency of Project HATID PANGARAP.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP at Hulo Integrated National High School and Hulo Elementary School during the first quarter of the School Year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought answers to the following research problems.

1. What is the evaluation of the teachers on the implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP with respect to its:
 - 1.1. objectives;
 - 1.2. program process;
 - 1.3. community involvement; and
 - 1.4. project monitoring and evaluation?
2. What are the limitations experienced by the teachers during the conduct of the implementation of the program?
3. What are the suggestions of the respondents to further improve the implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP?

Literature Review

Student absenteeism is defined as the period of not attending to school. It also refers to the persistent absences from work, school, meeting and the likes. According to Lannegrand-Willems et al. (2012), when a child missed some of the classes or not present at the school with or without a valid excuse, it fell on absenteeism.

Likewise, the attendance of the students in school is one variable that affect the students' academic performance and may not attain the success of life. One study of Gottfried (2010) revealed that academic achievement and school attendance has a positive relationship in attaining high scores in the chosen field or course. When students were absent, it may lead to academic failure and other possible risk factors (Demir & Akman, 2015).

Relatively, transportation issues such as buses not coming to the house, risky roads, traffic, and overloaded vehicle will impart a great impact on the student's ability not to go to school. Minor contributions such as no allowance or no snacks are also considered a factor. This means that students' absenteeism in high school leads to more negative effects on academic learning and social problems (Abdul et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the community has played a vital role in shaping and molding the educational system of the Philippines. Its contribution to the educational system in producing meaningful and productive citizens can never be denied. This is mainly due to the fact that when the school and the community have learned to cooperate with one another, many opportunities will arise to unite their efforts and materials on projects for community development (Sanders 2010).

A cordial relationship between the school and community is a pre-requisite for achieving a meaningful educational objective in the community and nation at large (Ferlazzo, 2011).

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive method of research was used in this study. Siedlecki (2020) defined what is descriptive research. He stated that a researcher studied the variables as they appear in their natural context and no manipulation is done. Survey questionnaire is used in descriptive method which is useful for collecting information from a group to describe characteristics of the population. In addition, it involves the collection and analysis of data about people or materials with the intention to compare existing and required standards.

Respondents

Thirty (30) teachers served as the respondents in this study. They were chosen purposively by the researchers since they were the ones who are involved in the implementation of the program, and they know its process.

Instrument

Online survey questionnaire using the Google Form served as the main research instrument in data gathering. The link was sent to the respondents and the researchers monitored the answers to ensure accurate and credible information.

Procedure

Online survey questionnaire was administered through Google Form to gather the needed data. The link was sent to the respondents to determine their evaluation on the implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP in terms of its objectives, program process, community involvement, and project monitoring and evaluation. It was also used to gather suggestions from the respondents for further improvement of the project. The researcher herself monitored the online form to make sure that it served its purpose to answer the

research problems presented in this paper.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Evaluations of Teachers on the Implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP with respect to Selected Aspects

Table 1. Evaluation of the Teachers on the Implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP in terms of Objectives

Objectives	Teachers	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The program encourages the learners to attend their classes	3.87	Strongly Agree
2. The program reduces the burden of the learners and their families concerning their access on various mode of transportation	3.87	Strongly Agree
3. The program motivates the learners which lead to their increased academic performance.	3.87	Strongly Agree
4. The program promotes inclusivity and equity in education.	4.00	Strongly Agree
5. The program establishes strong collaboration among stakeholders.	3.60	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.87	Strongly Agree

The table shows that the evaluation of the teachers on the implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP with respect to its objectives obtained an overall mean of 3.87 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

It can be glanced that the respondents believe that the program serves its primary purpose which is to promote inclusivity and equity in education. This implies that the project has essential guides that lead the teachers to achieve the desired outcomes and achieve its targets.

Table 2. Evaluation of the Teachers on the Implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP in terms of Program Process

Process	Teachers	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The project implementer conducted orientation about Project HATID PANGARAP for the teachers and students.	3.73	Strongly Agree
2. The project implementer formulated audit checklist, policies and procedures to govern the conduct of activities.	3.60	Strongly Agree
3. The teachers follow the activities as stated in the plan of action.	3.80	Strongly Agree
4. The school clearly establish mechanisms in implementing the program.	3.80	Strongly Agree
5. Everyone plays vital roles as members of the educational community in achieving the shared goals and responsibilities on Project HATID PANGARAP.	3.50	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.83	Strongly Agree

It can be seen on the table that the evaluation of the respondents on the implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP in terms of program process gained an overall mean of 3.83 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This indicates that the teachers concur with the idea that the program process of the program is followed and carried out properly. It implies that the involvement of all the people, internal and external members of the educational community, in the implementation is important; thus, they should be aware of all the aspects of Project HATID PANGARAP.

Table 3. Evaluation of the Teachers on the Implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP in terms of Community Involvement

Community Involvement	Teachers	
	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The stakeholders assist the school in sourcing out funds for the free transportation.	3.90	Strongly Agree
The members of the school community served as volunteers during the implementation of the project.	3.70	Strongly Agree
3. The stakeholders participate as advocates of Project HATID PANGARAP.	3.90	Strongly Agree
4. The members of the community involved themselves in the school-based and community-based activities related to Project HATID PANGARAP.	3.90	Strongly Agree
5. The school and the community establish strong collaboration for the success of Project PANGARAP.	3.70	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.82	Strongly Agree

It can be seen on the table that the evaluation of the respondents on the implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP in terms of community involvement gained an overall mean of 3.82 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This signifies that the teachers recognize the significance of the involvement of the members of the educational community in the success of the project. On the other hand, it should be noticed that the statements in this criterion all fall in Strongly Agree level of evaluation indicating that the school should work on how to build linkages from external stakeholders which may greatly enhance the implementation of the project through the support that can be provided by these individuals or groups.

It implies that participation of stakeholders is inevitable in the school initiatives especially those which need strong aids like fund and other sources that would help the implementer achieve the shared goals and responsibilities leading to its success.

Table 4. *Evaluation of the Teachers on the Implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP in terms of Monitoring and Evaluation*

	<i>Monitoring and Evaluation</i>	<i>Teachers</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The project has a well-defined monitoring tool that is utilized every quarter to identify the gaps in the implementation.		3.60	Strongly Agree
2. The teachers and students are involved in monitoring and evaluation process of Project Hatid Pangarap.		3.40	Strongly Agree
3. The results of the evaluations are presented to the stakeholders to educate everyone about cleanliness and safety of the school environment.		3.60	Strongly Agree
4. The project proponent identifies the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats throughout the implementation of the project.		3.70	Strongly Agree
5. The project has effective mechanism to monitor and evaluate the project.		3.20	Strongly Agree
	Overall Mean	3.5	Strongly Agree

The table illustrates that the evaluation of the respondents on the implementation of Project HATID PANGARAP in terms of monitoring and evaluation gained an overall mean of 3.5 verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree. It suggests that the respondents believe that the program follows systematic monitoring and evaluation of the conduct of the project from the start up to the end of its implementations. This implies that Project HATID PANGARAP has a good way of identifying the success indicators of the programs and its areas for improvement.

Conclusions

The findings of the study showed that the respondent provided positive evaluation on the implementation of the school initiative as to its objectives, process, monitoring and evaluation, and stakeholders involvement. In addition, limitations among the teachers were identified by them which challenged them during its implementation. Furthermore, significant suggestions were provided by the respondents that may serve as basis for further improvement of Project HATID PANGARAP.

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